

Determinants of Work life Balance on Lecturer Performance mediated by Work Engagement

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ABSTRACT: In a dynamic and demanding academic environment, achieving optimal work-life balance is crucial for the well-being and performance of faculty members. This research investigates the determinants of work-life balance among lecturers and explores the mediating role of work engagement in influencing lecturer performance. The study employs a quantitative method with a systematic review. A questionnaire-based survey was designed to test the model based on a dataset from 98 private lecturers in Banten. The partial results indicate that Work-Life Balance (WLB) and Work Engagement (WE) have a positive and significant impact on Lecturer Performance (EP). The research also reveals that WE plays a crucial mediating role, influencing the relationship between work-life balance and lecturer performance. This study is one of the few that explores the interconnections among WLB, Lecturer Performance, and Work Engagement (WE) as a crucial mediating variable.

KEYWORDS: Lecturer performance, Work life Balance, Work Engagement

INTRODUCTION

With the advancement of technology, the world has undergone globalization, creating high levels of competition among various organizations. These organizations adopt diverse strategies to achieve success and confront the intense competition (Dilhani & Dayarathna, 2017). Dynamics of change in the higher education environment demand adaptation in workforce skills. Therefore, efforts to enhance and develop new knowledge and skills within the workforce become a necessity pursued by universities to achieve their goals. (Menon & Suresh, 2021). Therefore, the balance of well-being among lecturers can enhance their own performance. Currently, this era is actively seeking solutions to enhance operational efficiency and productivity within organizations (J. Kim et al., 2022). According to research findings Angin & Saragih (2021), organizations make strenuous efforts to improve their performance in order to compete effectively. In facing this competition, managers encounter various challenges that need to be overcome. One common strategy employed by organizations is to provide the necessary job resources for employees, such as support. This type of support not only helps foster positive emotions among employees but also provides valuable reasons for them to engage fully in their work (Aldabbas et al., 2021).

Work-life balance is a crucial issue for every employee, whether in government agencies or private sector, especially in Indonesia. Organizations that can balance work and life are better prepared to address challenges stemming from multicultural and global markets. Therefore, these organizations gain a competitive advantage compared to those that are not sensitive and do not diversify in issues related to work-life balance for their employees (Keino & Kithae, 2016). This is because there will be a decrease in productivity and employee performance if an organization does not carefully consider and manage the work-life balance of its employees. In fact, nowadays, employees emphasize work-life balance more than just income, especially as many workplaces are now filled with the millennial generation that values job flexibility and is closely connected to technology. The important implication of this emerging behavior for achieving high company and employee performance is that companies must implement work-life balance policies to motivate employees and encourage their commitment to work optimally for the company (Wolor et al., 2020). Rachmadini & Riyanto (2020) argue that the conflict between work and family has tangible consequences. It significantly affects the quality of family life and career achievements for both men and women. Work-life balance is a crucial phenomenon that garners significant attention from various employees in both the private and public sectors. It goes beyond simply prioritizing one's work and personal life roles. It also influences the social, psychological, economic, and mental well-being of individuals. All these aspects

are reflected in individual outcomes, which affect long-term workplace performance. Work-life balance has been proven to have implications on attitudes, behaviors, well-being, and organizational effectiveness. (Obiageli et al., 2015).

The research findings by Sabir & Cura (2021) indicate that academic professionals indeed face challenges in achieving work-life balance in their careers. These challenges appear to be more pronounced for employees in private universities compared to those in public institutions. Public university employees tend to experience a better work-life balance, although the level of work-life balance culture in public universities may not be considered satisfactory. These results underscore the importance of understanding the dynamics of work-life balance in the academic context, as it can impact the mood, focus, and actions of employees in the workplace. (Angin & Saragih, 2021). Work-life balance is more than just prioritizing one's work and personal roles in life. It also influences the social, psychological, economic, and mental well-being of individuals. All of these aspects are reflected in individual outcomes, which impact long-term workplace performance (Salolomo & Agbaeze, 2019).

The research gap, according to Ardiansyah & Surjanti (2020) suggests that the variables of work-life balance and performance do not have a relationship.. According to the study by Riyanto et al. (2021), employee engagement indeed does not have a direct impact on employee performance. In a recent study within a large company, the inability to balance work and personal life, coupled with family life, was tied to compensation as the primary reason employees cited for their potential inclination to leave the company (Hill et al., 2001). According to the research by Moghaddam et al. (2022), it is shown that factors related to work-life balance not only have a direct effect but also indirectly influence work-life balance through emotional intelligence. Therefore, work-life balance is crucial for employees in a company, as it is influenced by factors that have both direct and indirect effects, particularly through emotional intelligence.

The knowledge gap addressed by this research revolves around an incomplete understanding of the direct impact of work-life balance on employee performance and the mediating role of Work Engagement. Therefore, this study aims to bridge existing knowledge gaps by empirically investigating the impact of work-life balance on lecturer performance in Banten. The researchers also collaborate with other scholars in an effort to uncover the effects of work-life balance on lecturer performance in Banten.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work life Balance

Fundamentally, work-life balance plays a significant role for every employee, indicating that employees achieve a balanced quality of life between work and personal life (Anugrah & Priyambodo, 2021). Research by Mercado (2019) describes work-life balance as a concept with three related components: "Time balance," "Engagement balance," and "Satisfaction balance." Work-life balance provides an indication of support for employees' efforts to manage their time and energy among family, work, and other essential aspects of their lives. Work-life balance plays a crucial role in selecting a healthy work environment and is closely related to maintaining a balance between personal and professional life (Irfan et al., 2023). Work-Life Balance, according to Lukmiati et al. (2020), is an individual's ability to maintain a balance between work responsibilities and personal needs outside the scope of work. In this study, the indicators used, as explained by Ardiansyah & Surjanti (2020), include balancing responsibilities toward family or the company, allocating work time and other needs, maintaining a healthy social life outside the company, and setting aside time for hobbies.

Work Engagement

According to Kahn (1990), work engagement refers to a situation in which employees play an active role in their work, participating physically, emotionally, and cognitively to fulfill their tasks. Znidaršič & Marič (2021) explain that work engagement involves the emotional and psychological relationship between employees and their organizations. Therefore, work engagement has become a crucial topic in current human resource management, especially as it is closely related to organizational productivity. Work engagement, as described by Wajong et al. (2020), is a desirable psychological state, characterized by resilience and inclusive of positive performance behaviors. It encompasses enthusiasm, happiness, and effort driven by spirit, dedication, and absorption. Anaya et al. (2023) add that the balance between employees' work and personal life can enhance their level of engagement in their work. Rachmadini & Riyanto (2020) state that employee engagement is key to improving a company's success, as efficiency and productivity are essential prerequisites in facing intense market competition.

Employment Performance

According to Abualoush et al. (2018), employee performance is defined as behavioral responses that reflect what employees have learned or been trained on, and it is a product of mental and psychological abilities. Performance is a stage of achievement as work accomplishment by an individual in an organization. Work performance in an organization is greatly influenced by three main factors: organizational support, managerial capability or effectiveness, and the performance of each individual working in that organization, where each unit in an organization has several divisions with individuals. According to Eliyana (2019), work achievement is influenced by organizational support, managerial capability, and the performance of each individual in the organization. Soomro et al. (2018) state that an employee's work results from their efforts as a reward for tangible and intangible benefits. In this context, research indicates that employees who enjoy greater participation in decision-making are more productive than those who do not.

Conceptual Framework and Model Hypotheses

The relationship between work-life balance and employee performance

An organization that implements work-life balance stands to gain benefits such as increased employee productivity and the ability to address conflicts, leading to a more tranquil work environment. Additionally, companies may experience positive influences from the enhanced performance of employees (Anugrah & Priyambodo, 2021). According to Angin & Saragih (2021), simultaneously, work-life balance affects employee performance. According to Dilhani & Dayarathna (2017), it is revealed that leave arrangements, flexible work schedules, and supportive family employment policies have a positive impact on employee performance. It means that Work-Life Balance in an organization has a positive impact on the performance of its employees. Work-life balance programs implemented in a company are expected to improve the level of employee performance, thereby fostering enthusiasm for work among employees in fulfilling their tasks and responsibilities towards the company (Herlambang & Murniningsih, 2017). Employees who exert their best efforts for the company as a gesture of gratitude can contribute to improved performance. Therefore, employees with a high level of work-life balance can be highly productive and perform exceptionally well (Susanto et al., 2022).

H1: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence of work-life balance on employee performance.

The relationship between work life balance and work engagement

According to the research by Mache et al. (2013) (cited in Anaya et al., 2023), it is also affirmed that family-friendly practices adopted by an organization have an impact on enhancing work engagement. Therefore, employees' ability, with organizational support, to achieve work-life balance is likely to lead to higher work engagement, increased commitment, and improved job performance (Anaya et al., 2023). According to Jaharuddin & Zainol (2019), engagement enables employees to become effective leaders who carry out their responsibilities. Therefore, a company with the right employee engagement conditions possesses a competitive advantage that is challenging for other companies in the market to replicate.

H2: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence of work-life balance on work engagement.

The relationship work engagement and employee performance

Employees who feel engaged tend to be more motivated to perform their jobs well. They feel connected to the organization's goals and believe that their contributions have a meaningful impact (Lai et al., 2020). According to Barko et al. (2022), engaged employees tend to be more productive because they have high job satisfaction. They are more likely to work hard and stay focused on achieving organizational goals, leading to improved performance. According to Ismail et al. (2019), employee engagement and performance are correlated, as engaged employees are expected to exhibit better performance compared to their disengaged counterparts. Relevant research, as indicated by Rajabalee et al. (2020), suggests that engagement in a constructivist environment may be a predictor of better success than engagement in a classic behavioral e-learning model.

H3: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence of work engagement on employee performance.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), enabling simultaneous analysis of a series of relationships and providing statistical efficiency. Structural Equation Modeling is employed to test research hypotheses (Ricardianto et al., 2020). Previous researchers have also noted the use of SEM models aided by the SmartPLS program (Akter et al., 2017). The data collection method in this study involves using a questionnaire through Google Forms (Kumarasamy et al., 2022). The research focuses on private lecturers in the Southern Banten region (Serang city, Serang district, Cilegon city, Lebak district, and Pandeglang district). The returned sample size is 98 lecturers. The measurement of all items is assessed on a six-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, with categories including strongly disagree, disagree, uncertain, agree, and strongly agree (Wang et al., 2019).. Work-life balance is measured using 5 (five) items, engagement is measured using 4 (four) items, while employee performance is measured using 5 (five) items.

RESULTS AND FINDING

Results of Model Feasibility Testing (Inner Model)

The three criteria used by the researcher in testing the data quality with SmartPLS to assess the outer model (data quality) are Convergent Validity, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Individual reflective measures are considered high if they correlate more than 0.70 with the measured constructs (Hair et al., 2011). The output of the measurement model can be seen in figure 2.

Outer Model Result

The SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) analysis using SmartPLS in this study is utilized to assess the relationships between the variables Work Life Balance, Engagement, and employee performance.

Figure 2. Model Analysis Result

Based on Figure 2, the SmartPLS analysis results show that the factor loadings for the constructs of work motivation, job satisfaction, and craftsman performance exceed the required threshold, which is between 0.5 to 0.6. From this analysis, it can be concluded that each item has a factor loading value exceeding 0.5, indicating that all constructs, namely Work Life Balance, Engagement, and employee performance, have a high level of validity.

Next, reliability evaluation can be conducted by observing the values of Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). When the Composite Reliability values between constructs and their indicators achieve satisfactory results, surpassing 0.70, and the AVE values exceed 0.05, it can be inferred that reliability has been fulfilled. Details regarding the Composite Reliability and AVE results can be found in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variabel	Composite Reliability	AVE
Lecturer Performance (Y)	0,924	0,708
WLB (X2)	0,914	0,725
WLB (X1)	0,909	0,667

Source : The research results are processed

Table 1 shows that the results of Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct indicate good quality. These values align with Chin's perspective, stating that the results of Composite Reliability for each construct can be considered good and can be taken into account in the analysis to evaluate the relationships between constructs. This is because the obtained values exceed the established thresholds, which are more than 0.70 for Composite Reliability and more than 0.05 for AVE. Overall, the analysis results indicate that these variables have Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted values that surpass the thresholds, demonstrating good levels of reliability and average variability, and can be used in the subsequent stages of the research.

To address the research hypotheses, the P-values are as follows:

Table 2. Result For Inner WLBights

Korelasi	Original Sampel (O)	Sampel Mean (M)	Standar Deviation	T. Statistics	P Values
WE- EP	0,649	0,650	0,079	8,258	0,000
WLB - EP	0,374	0,368	0,074	5,002	0,000
WLB- WE	0,456	0,467	0,095	4,802	0,000

Source : The research results are processed

Based on the above Table 2 regarding hypothesis testing, it can be explained that:

1. The hypothesis test results related to the impact of the Work-Life Balance (WLB) variable on Employee Performance (EP) yield a value of 0.374, as reflected in its path coefficient. Considering the t-value of 5.002, which exceeds the critical t-table value of 1.960, and a P-value of 0.000, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.000 \leq 0.05$), it can be concluded that the influence is significant. This indicates a positive and significant partial effect of the WLB variable on EP, and thus, the first hypothesis can be accepted.
2. The hypothesis test results regarding the direction of the influence of the Work-Life Balance (WLB) variable on Work Engagement (WE) show a path coefficient of 0.456. Considering the t-value of 4.802, which exceeds the critical t-table value of 1.960, and a P-value of 0.000, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), it can be concluded that the influence is significant. Therefore, it can be interpreted that there is a positive and significant effect of the WLB variable on Work Engagement (WE), and thus, the second hypothesis can be accepted.

3. The hypothesis test results regarding the direction of the influence of the Work Engagement (WE) variable on Employee Performance (EP) show a path coefficient of 0.649. Considering the t-value of 8.258, which exceeds the critical t-table value of 1.960, and a P-value of 0.000, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), it can be concluded that the influence is significant. Therefore, it can be interpreted that there is a positive and significant partial effect of the WE variable on Employee Performance (EP), and thus, the third hypothesis can be accepted.

Mediation effect

The indirect impact of the Work-Life Balance (WLB) variable on Employee Performance (EP) through Work Engagement (WE) can be observed in the following Table 3.

Table 3. Indirect effect

Korelasi	Orginal Sampel (O)	Sampel Mean (M)	Standar Deviation	T. Statistics c	P Values
WLB-WE -EP	0,296	0,302	0065070	4,576	0,000

Source : The research results are processed

From the data in Table 3, it can be concluded that based on the results of the mediation calculation, the value is 0.296, as seen from the path coefficient. With a t-value of 4.576, which exceeds the critical t-table value of 1.960, and a P-value of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05, it can be concluded that the influence is positive and significant. Therefore, it can be said that WLB significantly and positively influences EP through the improvement of WE.

DISCUSSION

The relationship between work life balance and employee performance

The initial hypothesis in this study stated that when Work-Life Balance (WLB) is high, lecturer performance will improve. The test results show a positive and significant relationship between WLB and lecturer performance, thus confirming this hypothesis. This finding is consistent with the research conducted by Irfan et al. (2023), which states that performance is directly influenced by work-life imbalance and has serious implications for employees, organizations, and society. Imbalance in work-life also impacts the quality of life and the careers of employees. Research by Benito-Osorio et al. (2014) indicates that work-life balance helps improve performance, ultimately enhancing productivity. If an organization provides adequate options for its employees to manage their work and family roles, the organization will have the opportunity to achieve higher levels of performance from its employees (Soomro et al., 2018).

The relationship between work life balance and work engagement

The second hypothesis in this study stated that if Work-Life Balance (WLB) is high, the level of job satisfaction will also increase. The test results show a positive and significant correlation between WLB and Work Engagement (WE), thus confirming this hypothesis. This finding indicates that work-life balance has a positive impact on work engagement. The results align with the research conducted by Jaharuddin & Zainol (2019), which also found a positive and significant influence between WLB and Work Engagement. Additionally, the study by Rachmadini & Riyanto (2020) suggests that employees' ability to achieve work-life balance with company support can lead to higher work engagement, greater commitment, and better work performance.

The relationship between work engagement and employee performance

The third hypothesis proposed in this study states that if Work Engagement (WE) is high, then the performance of craftsmen will also be higher. The test results indicate a positive and significant relationship between WE and the performance of craftsmen, confirming the acceptance of this hypothesis. This suggests that the driving force of human resources, namely the presence of Work Engagement, contributes to the improvement of craftsmen's performance. This finding aligns with research conducted by Hermawan et al. (2020) indicating that Work Engagement (WE) significantly influences employee performance. The importance of employee engagement is also highlighted, identifying various aspects that significantly affect employee performance (Anitha, 2014). Better employee engagement can enhance team performance within the organizational context. Organizational commitment and citizenship

behavior play a mediating role in the relationship between employee engagement and team performance (Uddin et al., 2019). Employee engagement has a significant impact on perceived well-being, which in turn enhances task performance (M. Kim & Kim, 2020). Employee engagement has a significant and positive influence on organizational performance (Ahmed et al., 2020).

The Relationship between WLB and Employee Performance through WE

The results of the hypothesis testing on mediation indicate that the relationship between WLB and Employee Performance through WE is positively and significantly influential. This suggests that WLB towards the performance of private university lecturers in Banten through the variable WE will increase the performance of these lecturers.

CONCLUSION

The findings from this study indicate that Work-Life Balance (WLB) has a positive and significant impact on lecturers' performance, as well as a similarly significant influence on Work Engagement (WE). Furthermore, Work Engagement (WE) has also been proven to have a positive and significant effect on lecturers' performance. An interesting result is the ability of Work Engagement (WE) as a mediating variable in the relationship between Work-Life Balance (WLB) and lecturers' performance. The implication is that achieving a balance between work and personal life not only improves lecturers' direct performance but also through an increase in the level of work engagement. This underscores the importance of higher education management strategies that support work-life balance, not only to enhance direct productivity but also through employee engagement as a positive mediator in the relationship between Work-Life Balance (WLB) and lecturers' performance. These implications can assist in planning more effective human resource management policies and practices to enhance the well-being and performance outcomes of lecturers.

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